

The effect of oxygen impurities of helium atmospheric pressure plasma jet on the redox chemistry of cells

C Lazarou^{1,2}, C Anastassiou², I Topala³, A S Chiper³, I Mihaila⁴, V Pohoata³ and G E Georghiou^{1,2}

¹FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, 1678, Cyprus

²ENAL Electromagnetics and Novel Applications Lab, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, 1678, Cyprus

³Iasi Plasma Advanced Research Center (IPARC), Faculty of Physics, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi, Iasi 700506, Romania

⁴Integrated Center of Environmental Science Studies in the North-Eastern Development Region (CERNESIM), Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi, Iasi 700506, Romania

Abstract

Reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS) play a central role in the immune system and on disease progression and therefore are important in the therapeutic abilities of the atmospheric pressure plasma jet (APPJ) [1]. In addition to RONS, the APPJ induces an electric field (IEF) on the biological cells. It can be inferred that it is the *combination* of IEF and RONS and not just RONS that gives the APPJ its unique therapeutic abilities, such as selectively treating cancer[2]. In the case of helium APPJ it was found that the addition of oxygen impurities allowed for more effective treatment of cancer cells [3]. Putting it all together, the hypothesis is that the addition of oxygen causes higher IEF on cancerous cells causing electroporation and the introduction of RONS in the cells causing apoptosis.

In this abstract a two dimensional axisymmetric model is developed [4] for the APPJ with the following parameters: quartz tube for plasma production, internal diameter = 0.9mm, external diameter=1.5mm, distance to dielectric=2mm, applied voltage = 4 kV, 10 kHz. The results in Figure 1 show that an optimal amount of 1500 ppm oxygen causes IEF to almost double (from 35 to 67 kV/cm). The dielectric is a first step for the simulations with the next being of replacing it with a cell model. Underway are also experiments where the effect of different levels of oxygen impurities on the redox chemistry of healthy and cancerous cells will be investigated.

Figure 1. IEF on dielectric surface

References

- [1] D. B. Graves, "Low temperature plasma biomedicine: A tutorial review," *Phys. Plasmas*, vol. 21, no. 8, 2014.
- [2] J. Van der Paal, C. Verheyen, E. C. Neyts, and A. Bogaerts, "Hampering Effect of Cholesterol on the Permeation of Reactive Oxygen Species through Phospholipids Bilayer: Possible Explanation for Plasma Cancer Selectivity," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 7 VN-re, no. August 2016, p. 39526, 2017.
- [3] S. J. Kim, T. H. Chung, S. H. Bae, and S. H. Leem, "Induction of apoptosis in human breast cancer cells by a pulsed atmospheric pressure plasma jet," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 97, no. 2, pp. 1–3, 2010.
- [4] C. Lazarou, T. Belmonte, A. S. Chiper, and G. E. Georghiou, "Numerical modelling of the effect of dry air traces in a helium parallel plate dielectric barrier discharge," *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.*, vol. 55023, no. 25, p. 55023, 2016.